

The Path to Quantum Mechanics

(From Planck to Schrödinger)

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Abstract

In the following sections, I will explain in great detail the core content of Planck's paper, titled **On the Law of Distribution of Energy in the Normal Spectrum**, in which he derived the blackbody radiation law, marking the birth of quantum physics. I will show how and why the quantization assumption came about. Then, I will explain a major content of Einstein's paper, titled **On a Heuristic Point of View Concerning the Production and Transformation of Light**, in which he proposed that light, under some conditions, can be thought of as composed of energy quanta, to be called later photons, including the motivation behind that proposal. Then, I will explain the ingenious quantum derivation for the Planck's law of radiation carried out by Bose in the paper titled **Planck's law and the light quantum hypothesis**. Eventually, I will explain the core work of Schrödinger's paper, titled **Quantization as an Eigenvalue Problem**, and the train of thoughts that eventually led to our beloved Schrödinger equation. I promise, you will enjoy the ride.

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1 The blackbody radiation, Planck, and the birth of quantum physics.

The blackbody radiation problem posed a great challenge to theorists at the time. It was the first to suggest that a look back at physics was needed. So, in this section, I will discuss Planck's solution to the blackbody problem and how the quantum postulate came about.

In 1900, Planck developed a theory called the theory of electromagnetic radiation. The principles of that theory were the key to directing Planck down the right track. Planck concluded from that theory that in order to calculate the radiation density function, u , for a blackbody in thermal equilibrium, all one needs to do is to calculate the entropy, S , of a single vibrating oscillator, vibrating at a specific frequency ν with a vibrational energy U . The oscillators, according to Planck, are the particles that constitute the blackbody (he didn't believe in atoms Oops!) After calculating S , we can deduce the relation between the vibrational energy U and the temperature T through the equation $\frac{dS}{dU} = \frac{1}{T}$. Then, by expressing U as a function of T , we can simply obtain the function u from the equation $u = \frac{8\pi\nu^2 U}{c^3}$. Thus, the solution to the blackbody radiation problem boils down to calculating the right form for S . Let's now discuss the attempts made by Planck to calculate S .

Attempt 1: Planck defined S as a simple function of U and was satisfied that such a definition satisfies the conditions imposed by thermodynamics. At the time, Planck was convinced that defining S in that way was the only way out there to define S . Following the program previously outlined, Planck managed to get a form for u . However, the function he got was already known, and proved to be failure once before. The function was Wien's function, the function obtained by Wien for the same purpose.

Attempt 2: Further research showed Planck that other expressions for S lead to the same result. Therefore, he realized that another condition must be imposed in order to get one exact form for S . The condition, Planck figured, was the dependency of the total entropy S_N on the total energy U_N , when an infinitesimally small irreversible change, near thermal equilibrium, occurs to a system of N identical oscillators permanently existing in the same stationary radiation field, rather than the energy of an individual oscillator. Doing this didn't change anything cause he still got Wien's function. Therefore, Planck concluded that another condition must be found in order to be able to reach the correct and unique form for S .

Attempt 3 (the victory): Planck realized that, in order to solve the puzzle, he must look at the concept of entropy from a different perspective. What Planck did was borrowing Boltzmann's machinery for calculating entropy, much to his personal dismay. By that point, Planck had always believed in the absolute nature of entropy, a nature that doesn't depend on neither the constituents nor probabilities. However, Boltzmann's entropy made use of all of the above, so it wasn't, really, something Planck would wanna use, but he had no other choice.

In Planck's words, the work went as follows:

1-Entropy depends on disorder and this disorder, according to the electromagnetic theory of radiation for the monochromatic vibrations of a resonator when situated in a permanent stationary radiation field, depends on the irregularity with which it constantly changes its amplitude and phase, provided one considers time intervals large compared to the time of one vibration but small compared to the duration of a measurement. If amplitude and phase both remained absolutely constant, which means completely homogeneous vibrations, no entropy could exist and the vibrational energy would have to be completely free to be converted into work. The constant energy U of a single stationary vibrating resonator accordingly is to be taken as time average, or what is the same thing, as a simultaneous average of the energies of a large number N of identical resonators, situated in the same stationary radiation field, and which are sufficiently separated so as not to influence each other directly. It is in this sense that we shall refer to the average energy U of a single resonator. Then to the total energy,

$$U_N = NU \quad (1)$$

of such a system of N resonators there corresponds a certain total entropy,

$$S_N = NS \quad (2)$$

of the same system, where S represents the average entropy of a single resonator and the entropy SN depends on the disorder with which the total energy U_N is distributed among the individual resonators.

2-We now set the entropy SN of the system proportional to the logarithm of its probability W , within an arbitrary additive constant, so that the N resonators together have the energy U_N

$$S_N = k_B \ln W + C \quad (3)$$

In my opinion this actually serves as a definition of the probability W , since in the basic assumptions of electromagnetic theory there is no definite evidence for such a probability. The suitability of this expression is evident from the outset, in view of its simplicity and close connection with a theorem from kinetic gas theory.

3-It is now a matter of finding the probability W so that the N resonators together possess the vibrational energy U_N . Moreover, **it is necessary to interpret U_N not as a continuous, infinitely divisible quantity, but as a discrete quantity composed of an integral number of finite equal parts.** Let us call each such part the energy element; consequently we must set

$$U_N = P\epsilon, \quad (4)$$

where P represents a large integer generally, while the value of ϵ is yet uncertain.

So, as one can see, borrowing Boltzmann's machinery was the sole motivation that pushed Planck to think of energy quantization. The entire problem boils down now to just figuring out how to calculate the W appearing in equation (3). Planck hypothesized that W should be proportional to the number of permutations obtained by dividing the energy available to the system, $P\epsilon$, over the N oscillators. An example of such a permutation will look something like $(\epsilon, 4\epsilon, \dots, 2\epsilon)$ - an N -tuple. Each possible N -tuple is named a

complex, as Boltzmann once called it. If R is the number of ways in which one can form the aforementioned N -tuple. Then, it follows from the theory of permutations that

$$R = \frac{(N + P - 1)!}{(N - 1)!P!} \quad (5)$$

Because N and P are generally big numbers, one can drop the 1 in the numerator and denominator. So,

$$R = \frac{(N + P)!}{N!P!} \quad (6)$$

Basically, we're done with the physics, the rest is just algebra.

As we have stated before, Planck hypothesized that W is proportional to R . Therefore, $W=kR$. So,

$$\ln W = \ln(kR) = \ln R + \ln k = \ln R + \text{const} \quad (7)$$

With this in hand, equation (3) will now read

$$S_N = k_B \ln R + C \quad (8)$$

We can set the initial conditions such that $C=0$. Having done this, then

$$S_N = k_B \ln R \quad (9)$$

Before we go on, let's rewrite equation (6) with Stirling's approximation (in the first approximation), i.e., $N! = N^N$. So,

$$R = \frac{(N + P)^{N+P}}{N^N \cdot P^P} \quad (10)$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} S_N &= k_B \ln R = k_B \{ (N + P) \ln(N + P) - N \ln N - P \ln P \} \\ &\vdots \\ &= k_B N \left\{ \left(1 + \frac{U}{\epsilon} \right) \ln \left(1 + \frac{U}{\epsilon} \right) - \frac{U}{\epsilon} \ln \frac{U}{\epsilon} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

It follows from equation (2) that

$$S = k_B \left\{ \left(1 + \frac{U}{\epsilon} \right) \ln \left(1 + \frac{U}{\epsilon} \right) - \frac{U}{\epsilon} \ln \frac{U}{\epsilon} \right\} \quad (11)$$

So far so good. After the last equation, Planck went on a little tour to investigate Wien's displacement law, and what conditions it shall put on the expression for entropy. He figured that whatever the expression for entropy may turn out to be, it should be a function of $\frac{U}{\nu}$, i.e., $S = f(\frac{U}{\nu})$. Looking back at equation (11), Planck readily concluded that ϵ must be proportional to ν , i.e., $\epsilon \propto \nu$. In other words,

$$\epsilon = h\nu \quad (12)$$

Where h is a constant yet to be determined.

Putting it all together, then

$$S = k_B \left\{ \left(1 + \frac{U}{h\nu} \right) \ln \left(1 + \frac{U}{h\nu} \right) - \frac{U}{h\nu} \ln \frac{U}{h\nu} \right\} \quad (13)$$

The entropy is related to the temperature through the equation:

$$\frac{1}{T} = \frac{dS}{dU} \quad (14)$$

But,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dS}{dU} &= k_B \left\{ \left(1 + \frac{U}{h\nu} \right) \frac{\frac{1}{h\nu}}{\left(1 + \frac{U}{h\nu} \right)} + \ln \left(1 + \frac{U}{h\nu} \right) \frac{1}{h\nu} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{h\nu} \frac{U}{h\nu} \frac{h\nu}{U} - \frac{1}{h\nu} \ln \frac{U}{h\nu} \right\} \\ &\quad \vdots \\ &= \frac{K_B}{h\nu} \left\{ \ln \left(1 + \frac{U}{h\nu} \right) - \ln \frac{U}{h\nu} \right\} \\ &\quad \vdots \\ &= \frac{K_B}{h\nu} \left\{ \ln \left(\frac{1 + \frac{U}{h\nu}}{\frac{U}{h\nu}} \right) \right\} \\ &\quad \vdots \\ &= \frac{K_B}{h\nu} \left\{ \ln \left(\frac{h\nu}{U} + 1 \right) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$U = \frac{h\nu}{e^{h\nu/k_B T} - 1} \quad (15)$$

But,

$$u = \frac{8\pi\nu^2}{c^3} U \quad (16)$$

Therefore,

$$u = \frac{8\pi h\nu^3}{c^3} \cdot \frac{1}{e^{h\nu/k_B T} - 1} \quad (17)$$

With the success of this last equation, quantum physics was given birth to, and the fun brought by it began never to end.

2 Why light should be quantized according to Einstein.

Even though it's been quite obvious since Planck's work, back in 1901, that light itself should, as well, be considered to be composed of quanta of energy, since the blackbody problem was a problem concerning the interaction between matter and RADIATION, Planck didn't have the guts to go this far. He was conservative and hated the entire thing. So it had to wait 4 more years until Einstein took the stand and proposed it, in 1905, as we shall see in the following lines.

In 1905, Einstein suggested that, under certain conditions, we can imagine light as being composed of discrete units of energy. How did he do this? Well, he used entropy. According to Einstein, light with an energy E and a frequency in the range from ν and $\nu + d\nu$, that range was assumed to be falling completely within the region of validity of Wien's radiation law, initially contained in a container of volume V_0 , to be changed eventually to V , suffers a change in entropy, ΔS , given by

$$\Delta S = \frac{E}{\beta\nu} \ln \frac{V}{V_0} \quad (18)$$

where $\beta = \frac{h}{k_B}$, and it is known, since 1901, that its value is $4.86610^{-11} K \cdot s$. The above equation gives the change in entropy for monochromatic radiation with sufficiently low intensity. Interestingly enough, that change in entropy is the same, in form, as that for a system of an ideal gas undergoing a change between the same volumes. The entropy change for the latter is given by

$$\Delta S = \frac{nR}{N_A} \ln \frac{V}{V_0} \quad (19)$$

Where R is the universal gas constant, N_A is the Avogadro's number, and n is the number of gas molecules in the system. A comparison between equations (18) and (19) yields the following:

$$n = \frac{EN_A}{\beta\nu R} \rightarrow E = n \left(\frac{\beta R}{N_A} \right) \nu \quad (20)$$

The above equation says that the total energy of the light, under investigation, is an integer times $\left(\frac{\beta R}{N_A} \right) \nu$. This suggests that light is, indeed, composed of identical chunks of energy, each with an energy equals to $\left(\frac{\beta R}{N_A} \right) \nu$. From this, Einstein concluded that **a monochromatic light of low intensity with a wavelength in the range of validity of Wien's radiation law, behaves, thermodynamically, as if it is composed of discrete energy quanta.** Interestingly enough, when we calculate the value of the constant $\frac{\beta R}{N_A}$, we find that it equals to Planck's constant h ! So, not only the energies of the blackbody oscillators are quantized, but light itself is also quantized.

3 Bose, the Einsteinian quanta, and the blackbody radiation.

Despite Planck's success in reaching the correct mathematical formula for the radiation density of a blackbody at any temperature and wavelength, he used equations derived from classical physics, specifically Maxwell's equations. Therefore, attempts were made to re-derive Planck's radiation law. However, this time, starting from pure quantum postulates. Einstein tried to accomplish this, but, ultimately, he still used classical physics. The successful attempt to re-derive the law, starting from pure quantum postulates, was done by no one before the Indian physicist Bose. Bose started with the following assumptions:

Firstly, he took Einstein seriously and started by considering light as composed of energy quanta (photons), each having an energy $h\nu$.

Secondly, he considered the state of such a photon to exist in a six-dimensional phase space, the dimensions of which, consist of 3 spatial components and 3 momentum components. This means that any point in that space will be of the form (x, y, z, p_x, p_y, p_z) . The following is a relation that connects the components of momentum and the frequency of a photon:

$$(p_x)^2 + (p_y)^2 + (p_z)^2 = \frac{h^2\nu^2}{c^2} \quad (21)$$

So, if there is a space with axes p_x , p_y , and p_z , the above equation represents a sphere with a radius $\frac{h\nu}{c}$. Moving to the 6D phase space, the first thing you should know is that the volume of a region in such a space is given by

$$\int dx dy dz dp_x dp_y dp_z = \frac{4}{3}V\pi\left(\frac{h\nu}{c}\right)^3 \quad (22)$$

where V is the volume in the spatial space and $\frac{4}{3}\pi\left(\frac{h\nu}{c}\right)^3$ is the volume in the momentum space. The volume of a piece of this space where ν ranges from ν to $\nu + d\nu$ will be $4\pi V\left(\frac{h^3\nu^2}{c^3}\right)d\nu$. Bose proposed that the phase space consists of cells. The volume of such a cell, Bose proposed, is h^3 . With our knowledge of the volume in the phase space, then there are $4\pi V\frac{\nu^2}{c^3}d\nu$ available cells. A photon in any such a cell can have up to two states (2 microstates), given the possible polarization states. So, the total number of available states to photons is $8\pi V\left(\frac{\nu^2}{c^3}\right)d\nu$. This is the most important thing in Bose's work. It will eventually lead to his kind of statistical mechanics. After his proposal, Bose might have said something like "Okay, let's suppose this system is in thermal equilibrium." In thermal equilibrium, the photons distribute themselves in the available cells in such a way that the state (macrostate) they occupy is the state with the largest number of possible arrangements (the largest number of microstates). The question now is, how did Bose manage to get the equilibrium's distribution? Well, all he had to do was

- 1-Write down the general form of a macrostate.
- 2- Find the number of different arrangements in the general macrostate.
- 3- Use calculus to calculate what macrostate gives the maximum number of arrangements.

The macrostate resulting from such a process is gonna be the thermal equilibrium macrostate. That macrostate will lead to Planck's law of radiation, marking the first ever successful

attempt at deriving the law from pure quantum postulates.

Now, let's get a bit more technical and show what exactly Bose did. Bose called the total number of available microstates for his system A^s , where s has just been used to indicate the range of frequencies available to photons, the frequencies in this s-range go from ν^s to $\nu^s + d\nu^s$. Bose divided the total number of states into numbers of sub states. A number of states where there is no photon at all, P_0^s , another number where there is only one photon, P_1^s , and a third number where there are 2 photons, P_2^s , etc. Therefore, if there is a number P_r^s where there are r photons, then $\sum_r P_r^s = A^s$. The total number of photons in the system is given, therefore, by the following:

$$N^s = \sum_r (rP_r^s) \quad (23)$$

Now, the possible ways to arrange all the states in A^s such that there is a number of states P_0^s having no photons at all, a number of states P_1^s having 1 photon, and a number P_r^s having r photons, will be

$$\frac{A^s!}{\prod_r P_r^s!}; \quad \prod_r P_r^s! = P_1^s! P_2^s! \dots P_r^s! \dots \quad (24)$$

When taking all ranges into consideration, the total number of arrangements becomes

$$W = \prod_s \left(\frac{A^s!}{\prod_r P_r^s!} \right) \quad (25)$$

At thermal equilibrium, the macrostate in which photons arrange themselves will be the state with the largest number of microstates. Therefore, all Bose did was figuring out when W is maximum, or equivalently, when $\ln W$ is maximum subject to the following constraints:

$$E = \sum_s N^s h\nu^s; \quad N^s = \sum_r (rP_r^s); \quad \sum_r P_r^s = A^s \quad (26)$$

So,

$$0 = \sum_s \delta N^s h\nu^s; \quad \delta N^s = \sum_r (r\delta P_r^s); \quad \sum_r \delta P_r^s = 0 \quad (27)$$

Therefore,

$$\ln W = \sum_s \ln \left(\frac{A^s!}{\prod_r P_r^s!} \right) = \sum_s \ln A^s! - \sum_s \sum_r \ln P_r^s! \quad (28)$$

Using Stirling's approximation, i.e., $\ln Q! = Q \ln Q$, then

$$\ln W = \sum_s \ln A^s! - \sum_s \sum_r \ln P_r^s! = \sum_s A^s \ln A^s - \sum_s \sum_r P_r^s \ln P_r^s \quad (29)$$

When $\ln W$ peaks, we find that $\delta \ln W = 0$, i.e., $\ln W$ is stationary. So,

$$\delta \ln W = \sum_s \sum_r \delta P_r^s \ln P_r^s + \delta P_r^s = \sum_s \sum_r \delta P_r^s (\ln P_r^s + 1) = 0 \quad (30)$$

Now, we will use Lagrange Multipliers to find P_r^s that will make $\ln W$, and therefore W , maximum while taking into consideration the constraints imposed. To impose the constraints, we do the following:

1-We multiply $0 = \sum_s h\nu^s \delta N^s$

by 1 over β where β is a constant.

2-We multiply $\sum_r \delta P_r^s$ by the constant $\sum_s \lambda^s$.

3-We add the results of 1 and 2 to equation (30).

Doing this gives,

$$\delta \ln W = \sum_s \sum_r \delta P_r^s (\ln P_r^s + 1 + \lambda^s) + \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_s h\nu^s \delta N^s = 0 \quad (31)$$

So,

$$\delta \ln W = \sum_s \sum_r \delta P_r^s (\ln P_r^s + 1 + \lambda^s) + \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_s h\nu^s \sum_r (r \delta P_r^s) = 0 \quad (32)$$

So,

$$\delta \ln W = \sum_s \sum_r \delta P_r^s (\ln P_r^s + 1 + \lambda^s) + \sum_s \sum_r \left(\frac{r h \nu^s}{\beta} \right) \delta P_r^s = 0 \quad (33)$$

Therefore,

$$\ln P_r^s + 1 + \lambda^s = -\frac{r h \nu^s}{\beta} \quad (34)$$

Or,

$$P_r^s = e^{-(1+\lambda)} e^{-\frac{r h \nu^s}{\beta}} \quad (35)$$

Let $e^{-(1+\lambda)} = B^s$, then

$$P_r^s = B^s e^{-\frac{r h \nu^s}{\beta}} \quad (36)$$

So far so good. What we need to do now is to rewrite B^s in terms of A^s . Recall that

$$\sum_r P_r^s = A^s$$

Therefore,

$$\sum_r B^s \exp\left(\frac{-r h \nu^s}{\beta}\right) = A^s \quad (37)$$

Therefore,

$$B^s = A^s \left(1 - \exp\left(\frac{-h \nu^s}{\beta}\right)\right)$$

Therefore,

$$P_r^s = A^s \left(1 - \exp\left(\frac{-h \nu^s}{\beta}\right)\right) e^{-\frac{r h \nu^s}{\beta}} \quad (38)$$

That last equation gives us what we once sought for, i.e., the form of P_r^s that maximizes $\ln W$, therefore, W . Now what? Well, now we have enough tools to calculate the total energy of the system, the target of all this after all. Recall that $E = \sum_s N^s h \nu^s$, but $N^s = \sum_r r p_r^s = \sum_r r A^s \left(1 - \exp\left(\frac{-h \nu^s}{\beta}\right)\right) e^{-\frac{r h \nu^s}{\beta}} =$

$$A^s \frac{\exp(-h \nu^s / \beta)}{1 - \exp\left(\frac{-h \nu^s}{\beta}\right)}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} E &= \sum_s h \nu^s A^s \frac{\exp(-h \nu^s / \beta)}{1 - \exp\left(\frac{-h \nu^s}{\beta}\right)} \\ &= \sum_s h \nu^s A^s \frac{1}{\exp\left(\frac{h \nu^s}{\beta}\right) - 1} \end{aligned}$$

But, $A^s = \frac{8\pi V(\nu^s)^2 d\nu^s}{c^3}$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} E &= \sum_s h\nu^s \left(\frac{8\pi V(\nu^s)^2 d\nu^s}{c^3} \right) \frac{1}{\exp(\frac{h\nu^s}{\beta}) - 1} \\ &= \sum_s \frac{8h\pi V(\nu^s)^3 d\nu^s}{c^3} \frac{1}{\exp(\frac{h\nu^s}{\beta}) - 1} \end{aligned}$$

Which is completely equivalent to the Planck's radiation law.

With this result, Einstein's quanta, once highly doubtful, are now rested on a solid ground.

4 Schrödinger's equation and how it came to be.

In 1924, de Broglie proposed that not only light behaves like particles, but also particles behave like waves. He introduced an equation through which one can calculate the wavelength of the proposed matter wave associated with a moving particle. However, he didn't provide much about what actually this wave is. If there is a wave, as Debye once said, then there must be an equation. Where is the equation? This is what Schrödinger provided in 1926. So, how Schrödinger got his equation? This is what I am gonna talk about in this section.

Schrödinger started out with a simple system, a system of a particle in a conservative force field. Then, he wrote down the Hamilton-Jacobie equation for that system as follows:

$$H(\vec{p}, \vec{q}) + \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (39)$$

The solution to this equation will give the p's and q's of that system as a function of time. This is a conservative system, so

$$H(\vec{p}, \vec{q}) = \frac{\vec{p} \cdot \vec{p}}{2m} + V(x, y, z) \quad (40)$$

Therefore equation (39) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{\vec{p} \cdot \vec{p}}{2m} + V(x, y, z) + \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (41)$$

Now, I'll ask you to trust me with the following equation:

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial q_i} = p_i \quad i = x, y, \text{ or } z \quad (42)$$

Till this point, I haven't said anything about what the function S is, it's time now. Well, S is the action function, and it's defined through the following:

$$S = \int_{t_0}^t L d\tau \quad (43)$$

The solution to equation (41) means finding the function S that is gonna satisfy it. It turns out that S is gonna be a solution to (41) provided it is written as $W(x, y, z) - Et$, E being the energy of the system. What Schrödinger was interested in wasn't how to solve equation(41), but he was interested in deriving some insights from the form of the solution. To this desire, Schrödinger substituted with $S = W(x, y, z) - Et$ back in (41) and hoped for the best. Let's do this.

$$\frac{\vec{p} \cdot \vec{p}}{2m} + V + \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (44)$$

So,

$$\frac{1}{2m} (p_x^2 + p_y^2 + p_z^2) + V + \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (45)$$

Then,

$$\frac{1}{2m} \left(\left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right) + V + \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (46)$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{1}{2m} \left(\left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right) = E - V \quad (47)$$

Finally,

$$|\vec{\nabla} W| = \sqrt{2m(E - V)} \quad (48)$$

Keep this result aside; we're gonna need it down the road. Now begins the best part. Schrödinger might have said "Let's equate S to a constant," i.e., $S = W(x, y, z) - Et = C$. Now, recall that $\frac{\partial S}{\partial q_i} = p_i$. Stare a little bit at it, what do you notice? Exactly, you conclude that $\vec{\nabla} S = \vec{p}$. But wait a sec, isn't $\vec{\nabla} S$ perpendicular to $S=C$? But $\vec{\nabla} S = \vec{p}$, therefore, \vec{p} is also perpendicular to $S=C$; Can you see where am I going with this? From the above discussion, we get to an interesting conclusion. We conclude that the mechanical trajectory is gonna always be perpendicular to the surface with constant action, AMAZING! Indeed, we conclude that all possible mechanical trajectories are gonna be perpendicular to the surface with constant action. Doesn't that ring a bell? Well, the aforementioned scenario is identical to the scenario in ray optics, except for minor changes. In ray optics, a particle of light follows a path that is perpendicular to the surface with constant phase, the wavefront. So, with this striking similarity between the two scenarios, one can guess that what can be applied to the latter can be applied to the former. Now recall that ray optics is a limitation to wave optics. Therefore, in the same way, Schrödinger concluded that mechanics as described by the Hamilton-Jacobi equation is, indeed, also a limitation to a more broader view called the wave mechanics, AMAZING! What Schrödinger is gonna do next is to find that wave equation whose solution is gonna be the wave function that, under specific conditions, boils down to the normal mechanics. Schrödinger is gonna work out this last problem bottom-up, i.e., starting with the result of all this (the wave function). Therefore, Schrödinger started by assuming the following to be a possible candidate for the wave function:

$$\psi = A(x, y, z) \sin(\text{phase}) \quad (49)$$

But, what should be put as the phase of this function? Recall that the surface with a constant action acted the same role as the surface with a constant phase. This suggests that instead of the word "phase," one should put S. However, one should put S/K, instead, to clear up the units. So far so good. With that being said and done, then

$$\psi = A(x, y, z) \sin\left(\frac{S}{K}\right) \quad (50)$$

Recall that $S = W - Et$, then

$$\psi = A(x, y, z) \sin\left(\frac{W}{K} - \left(\frac{E}{K}\right)t\right) \quad (51)$$

We wanna know what value the constant K should take. In order to do this, we shall compare the candidate function in the above with the typical form of a wave function,

i.e., with $\varphi = B(x, y, z) \sin(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega t)$. That being said and done, then

$$\omega = 2\pi\nu = \frac{E}{K} \quad (52)$$

Therefore,

$$K = \frac{E}{2\pi\nu} \rightarrow K = \hbar \quad (53)$$

Therefore,

$$\psi = A(x, y, z) \sin\left(\frac{S}{\hbar}\right) \quad (54)$$

Schrödinger now that he has the final form of ψ , will try to find the equation that can be solved via ψ . He will do this simply by plugging with the above form of ψ in the normal wave equation, that is, in the equation

$$u^2 \nabla^2 \psi = \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} \quad (55)$$

However, there is yet one thing to be determined, the phase speed u (we used the same letter to mean something different in the first section, so don't get confused). The procedure through which u is determined, is as follows:

$$S = W - Et = \text{const} \quad (56)$$

So,

$$dS = dW - E dt = 0 \quad (57)$$

So,

$$dW = E dt \quad (58)$$

But, $dW = |\nabla \vec{W}| dn$. Therefore,

$$|\nabla \vec{W}| dn = E dt \quad (59)$$

So,

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = \frac{E}{|\nabla \vec{W}|} = u \quad (60)$$

Recall that

$$|\nabla \vec{W}| = \sqrt{2m(E - V)} \quad (61)$$

Therefore,

$$u = \frac{E}{\sqrt{2m(E - V)}} \quad (62)$$

So, we now have

$$\psi = A(x, y, z) \sin\left(\frac{S}{\hbar}\right) \quad (63)$$

Or,

$$\psi = A(x, y, z) \sin\left(\frac{W}{\hbar} - \left(\frac{E}{\hbar}\right) t\right) \quad (64)$$

And,

$$\mathbf{u} = \frac{E}{\sqrt{2m(E - V)}} \quad (65)$$

Let's substitute with these in

$$u^2 \nabla^2 \psi = \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} \quad (66)$$

Upon doing this, we get

$$\left(\frac{E^2}{2m(E - V)} \right) \nabla^2 \psi = \left(\frac{-E^2}{\hbar^2} \right) \psi \quad (67)$$

With a little rearranging, we get

$$\left(\frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \right) \nabla^2 \psi + V\psi = E\psi \quad (68)$$

Which is the celebrated (time independent) Schrödinger equation. A generalisation to non conservative systems and any number of particle will lead to the full time depended Schrödinger equation

$$\left(\frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \right) \nabla^2 \psi + V\psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} \quad (69)$$

5 References.

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6-Planck's picture on the cover was adopted from [here](#).

7-Einstein's picture on the cover page was adopted from [here](#).

8-Bose's picture on the cover page was adopted from [here](#).

9-Schrödinger's picture on the cover page was adopted from [here](#)

10-The Schrödinger's equation engraved on his gravestone picture was adopted from [here](#).